

PROTECTION OF HUMAN RIGHTS OF ILLEGAL MIGRANT WORKERS: AN INTERNATIONAL LEGAL PERSPECTIVE

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Abstract

The increase in international migration has led to a growing number of migrant workers in irregular or illegal situations, especially from developing countries such as Indonesia. In reality, illegal migrant workers are often seen solely as violators of immigration laws, so their presence is often associated with repressive actions such as detention and deportation. In addition, the presence of illegal migrant workers often creates vulnerabilities, including exploitation, discrimination, human trafficking, and limited access to justice. This study aims to analyze the understanding of human rights protection for illegal migrant workers and state responsibilities in the context of international law. The method used in this study is normative legal research with a legislative and conceptual approach, through an analysis of international legal instruments such as the Universal Declaration of Human Rights, ICCPR, ICESCR, and ILO Convention No. 143 of 1975. The research findings show that illegal migration status does not eliminate the basic rights of migrant workers as individuals with human rights. The state is responsible for respecting, protecting, and fulfilling the rights of illegal migrant workers without discrimination. This protection includes the right to decent working conditions, fair wages, protection from exploitation, and access to justice. Therefore, migration policies based on human rights and alignment of national laws with international legal standards are needed to ensure humane and fair protection for irregular migrant workers.

Keywords: Human Rights, Illegal Migrant Workers, International Law, ILO

INTRODUCTION

Migration, as a process of population movement, has increased significantly in recent decades, particularly in developing countries, including Indonesia. This surge in migration flows is particularly evident from regions of origin to destinations. Limited job opportunities at home drive workers to seek employment abroad. This is evidenced by a growing trend over the years, driven by several factors such as inadequate domestic job opportunities, rising domestic unemployment rates, advances in technology and information, global growth disparities, and the right to work abroad. This is a significant socio-economic phenomenon in Southeast Asia, particularly in Indonesia and Thailand. Both countries play a strategic role as sending and receiving countries for migrant workers, making significant contributions to national and regional economic development. Data shows that Indonesia is one of the largest sending countries for migrant workers in the world, while Thailand is a major destination for migrant workers, particularly from neighboring countries such as Myanmar, Cambodia, and Laos. Illegal migrant workers are often viewed solely as violators of immigration laws, and their presence is often associated with repressive measures such as detention and deportation. Furthermore, the presence of illegal migrant workers often creates vulnerabilities, including exploitation, discrimination, human trafficking, and limited access to justice. This approach often ignores the fact that illegal migrant workers are human beings with inherent dignity and fundamental rights. From the perspective of international human rights law, immigration status should not be a reason to eliminate or reduce a person's basic rights. The principle of the universality of human rights affirms that everyone has the right to human rights protection without discrimination, including on the basis of nationality or migration status. From an international human rights perspective, the presence of an illegal migrant worker does not deprive them of their basic human rights. The principle of universality of human rights states that everyone, regardless of citizenship or immigration status, has the right to human rights protection, particularly the right to dignity, safety at work, and protection from exploitation. This principle aligns with the human security approach, which places the individual as the primary focus of international legal protection. International human rights legal instruments, such as the Universal Declaration of Human Rights

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(UDHR), affirm that all individuals are born free and equal in dignity and rights. This principle is reinforced by the International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights (ICCPR) and the International Covenant on Economic, Social and Cultural Rights (ICESCR), which stipulate that the rights enshrined therein apply to "every individual" within a country's territory. Therefore, illegal migrant workers are entitled to protection of their right to life, freedom from torture, protection against forced labor, the right to receive their due wages, and access to justice. These principles are clearly reflected in the context of global labor law. The International Labour Organization (ILO) plays a vital role in protecting migrant workers, including those in undocumented or irregular conditions. The ILO consistently avoids the term "irregular migrant worker" as it is considered inconsistent with its human rights-focused approach. According to the ILO, unlawful immigration status is an administrative offense and should not deprive individuals of their fundamental rights as workers.

The International Labour Organization (ILO) Convention No. 143 of 1975 aims to examine the conditions of migrants who are vulnerable to abuse, and encourages increased equality and treatment for migrant workers, while still paying attention to and guaranteeing their rights, including human rights. These values include the protection of migrant workers in irregular migration situations, preventing exploitation, upholding human rights against human trafficking, promoting equal rights, and equitable economic integration of migrant workers in receiving countries. This Convention emphasizes that all migrant workers, regardless of documented status, must have fundamental rights. Article 1 of the Convention explicitly states that each member state of the Convention must respect the fundamental human rights of all migrant workers. This principle is in line with the ILO's mandate to promote and provide decent, safe, and dignified working conditions as stated in the Philadelphia Declaration.

In addition, international human rights law establishes clear responsibilities for states to protect irregular migrant workers through obligations to respect, protect, and fulfill human rights. Destination countries are responsible for preventing exploitation by employers and ensuring access to effective complaint mechanisms. Origin countries are obligated to provide consular protection and education on safe migration, while transit countries are responsible for preventing human trafficking and migrant smuggling. However, in practice, the implementation of these obligations still faces various challenges, including restrictive immigration policies, weak labor oversight, and irregular migrant workers' fear of accessing legal protection. Given this, this research is crucial for thoroughly examining how human rights protection and state responsibilities apply to irregular migrant workers from an international human rights perspective. This study is expected to provide a strong academic contribution to strengthening a human rights-based approach to handling irregular migrant workers and encouraging alignment of national immigration policies with international legal standards.

LITERATURE REVIEW

1. How do the concepts of human rights protection and state responsibility apply to illegal migrants?
2. What are the basic rights of illegal migrant workers in international human rights instruments?
3. What is the state's responsibility towards illegal migrant workers from an international human rights perspective?

METHOD

Research methodology is the knowledge of how to conduct research in an orderly and systematic manner. This research applies normative legal methods, which view law as a system of norms. The approaches used include a legislative approach and a conceptual approach. The legislative approach is carried out by analyzing international legal instruments related to human rights and employment, while the conceptual approach is used to explore the concept of human rights protection for illegal migrant workers. The analysis uses legal sources consisting of primary, secondary, and tertiary legal sources. Primary legal sources include the Universal Declaration of Human Rights, the International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights, the International Covenant on Economic, Social and Cultural Rights, the International Convention on the Protection of the Rights of All Migrant Workers and Members of Their Families, the ILO convention on migrant workers, and the Palermo Protocol. Secondary legal sources consist of books, articles in scientific journals, and official reports from the UN, ILO, and IOM.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The Concept of Human Rights Protection for Illegal Migrant Workers

In the context of international human rights law, the protection of human rights is based on universal principles, non-discrimination, and respect for human dignity. Universal principles affirm that human rights are inherent in every individual from birth, regardless of nationality, legal status, or status as a migrant. Therefore, illegal migrant workers are also recognized as legal subjects within the context of global human rights and are

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entitled to the same protections as other individuals. This principle is clearly reflected in the Universal Declaration of Human Rights (UDHR), which affirms that every person is born free and equal in rights and dignity. The Universal Declaration of Human Rights (UDHR) is a general standard stating that human rights must be protected internationally. This statement serves as a normative basis demonstrating that "illegal" immigration status does not deprive an individual of their fundamental rights. This principle is reinforced by the International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights (ICCPR), which states in Article 2 that it requires states to ensure respect for the fundamental rights of everyone without discrimination, including for workers under their jurisdiction. In this context, migrant workers, including those in irregular migration status, remain considered human rights subjects who must be treated humanely and fairly. Therefore, human rights protection does not only apply to citizens or migrants who have official documents. In line with the principles of the UDHR and ICCPR, protection of migrant workers is also further developed in the ILO conventions governing labor migration.

Protection for undocumented migrant workers is clearly stipulated in the ILO Convention No. 143 of 1975 concerning Migrant Workers (Supplementary Provisions). Article 1 of this convention requires participating countries to respect the human rights of all migrant workers, regardless of their migration status, whether legal or not. This convention also requires countries to take effective measures to eradicate illegal labor recruitment and to impose sanctions on employers who exploit undocumented migrant workers. One of the most crucial is the ILO Convention No. 143 of 1975 concerning Migrant Workers (Supplementary Provisions). This convention was created in response to the increase in irregular migration, which is often accompanied by exploitation, human trafficking, and discrimination against undocumented migrant workers.

In Convention No. 143, the position of irregular migrant workers is understood within two main frameworks, namely the prevention of irregular migration and the protection of the basic rights of irregular migrant workers. This Convention emphasizes that ILO member states have a responsibility to prevent and reduce the rate of irregular migration. States are encouraged to implement legal, administrative measures, and international cooperation to eradicate illegal recruitment, black labor brokers, and human trafficking practices. This shows that irregular migrant workers are considered a migration phenomenon that needs to be controlled to maintain legal and international order. Despite their illegal immigration status, Convention No. 143 states that irregular migrant workers still have the right to receive fair and non-discriminatory treatment. Protected rights include, avoidance of discrimination in the workplace, the right to receive adequate remuneration and good working conditions, protection from exploitation, forced labor, and degrading treatment. With this provision, the ILO emphasizes that illegal status should not be used as a reason to eliminate the basic rights of migrant workers as human beings and workers.

Regarding illegal migrant workers, an understanding of human rights protection requires states to view migrants not merely as administrative violators but also as individuals at risk of becoming victims of human rights violations. Many undocumented migrant workers experience forced labor, excessive working hours, the withholding of documents by employers, and even physical and psychological violence. This situation demonstrates that a security-based approach is insufficient and needs to be replaced with a human rights-focused approach. While the principles contained in the Universal Declaration of Human Rights form the basis for the development of various international legal instruments, they also underlie the ILO International Labour Organization conventions governing international labor law. In the context of human rights, the ILO's obligation to protect migrant workers is typically carried out through the development and monitoring of international labor norms. It is important to remember that, unless there are different provisions for specific categories of workers, all ILO Conventions and Recommendations are of general application and cover all workers, whether nationals or non-nationals. This means that all ILO Conventions and Recommendations are relevant to all migrant workers, whether working temporarily or permanently, even if they are in irregular circumstances.

Basic Rights of Illegal Migrant Workers in International Human Rights Instruments

Despite their lack of official documentation, illegal migrant workers still enjoy a number of fundamental rights protected by international human rights law. These rights include the right to life, the right to be free from torture and inhumane treatment, the right not to be enslaved or forced to work, and the right to be recognized as an individual under the law. These rights are among the rights that cannot be derogated from under any circumstances. Article 23 of the Universal Declaration of Human Rights states: "Everyone has the right to work, to free choice of employment, to just and favorable conditions of work, and to protection against unemployment." Everyone, without any discrimination, has the right to equal pay for equal work. Everyone who works has the right to just and adequate remuneration ensuring a dignified existence for himself and his family, and may be supplemented, if necessary, by additional social protection. Everyone has the right to form and join trade unions to

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protect their interests. These provisions demonstrate that the right to work and protection in employment relations is an essential part of human rights. This principle is reinforced by Articles 6 and 7 of the International Covenant on Economic, Social and Cultural Rights (ICESCR), which emphasize that states parties to the covenant must guarantee the right to just and favorable conditions of work, the right to a decent wage, and the right to good health. The UN Committee on Economic, Social and Cultural Rights affirms that these rights apply to all workers without discrimination, including undocumented migrant workers. Therefore, states remain responsible for ensuring that illegal migrant workers are not economically exploited. In line with the principles of the UDHR and ICESCR, protection of migrant workers is further developed in the ILO conventions governing labor migration. ILO Convention No. 143, Article 1, affirms that undocumented migrant workers are entitled to protection of their rights arising from employment relationships, particularly the right to wages for work performed and protection against inhumane working conditions. ILO Convention No. 143, Article 2, affirms that violations of immigration status cannot be used as justification for employers to avoid legal responsibilities related to migrant workers. From an international legal perspective, ILO Convention No. 143 of 1975 not only regulates the governance of migrant workers but also regulates provisions to prevent and take action against human rights violations such as human trafficking and exploitation that migrant workers often experience. In addition, this Convention emphasizes the need for equal access to employment, social security, and the same legal protection as local workers in the receiving country. The ILO Convention that makes labor rights an integral part of human rights is reflected in the concept of "Fundamental Principles and Rights at Work," which includes freedom from forced labor, elimination of discrimination, and decent working conditions. These principles apply internationally to all workers, including illegal migrant workers.

State Responsibilities towards Illegal Migrant Workers from an International Human Rights Perspective

In the context of international human rights law, state responsibility is defined through three basic obligations: to respect, protect, and fulfill human rights. These obligations apply to all individuals within a state's jurisdiction, including undocumented migrant workers. Within the framework of government responsibility, international human rights law affirms that states are the primary party obligated to respect, protect, and ensure the fulfillment of the human rights of everyone within their jurisdiction. This responsibility extends not only to citizens but also to foreigners and unauthorized migrants. This aligns with the human rights provisions contained in the Indonesian constitution, which recognizes that human rights are inherent in every individual, not just the rights of citizens. The obligation to respect human rights requires states to refrain from actions that directly violate the rights of irregular migrant workers, such as arbitrary arrests or mass deportations without due process. The responsibility to protect requires states to prevent human rights violations by third parties, particularly exploitative employers or recruitment agencies. In this context, states are obligated to provide an effective labor inspection system and secure channels for complaints for irregular migrant workers. Under international human rights law, the responsibility to protect migrant workers lies not solely with one state, but also with both sending and receiving states. Sending states must ensure that their citizens working abroad receive protection from the pre-departure stage, including by providing adequate information, preventing irregular migration, and providing diplomatic support in the event of violations of migrant workers' fundamental rights.

On the other hand, receiving countries have an obligation to ensure the protection of human rights for migrant workers within their territory, without discrimination based on immigration status. This obligation includes protecting the rights to decent working conditions, fair compensation, workplace safety, and prevention of exploitation, violence, and forced labor. In this regard, migrant workers with irregular immigration status still have the right to protection of basic rights as part of universal human rights. From an implementation perspective, the application of Convention No. 143 of 1975 requires an effective monitoring system, effective bilateral and multilateral cooperation, and national regulations that align with international standards. Furthermore, the active involvement of trade unions, civil society, and international institutions such as the ILO is crucial to ensure that the principles of equality and non-discrimination can be realized domestically. Therefore, ILO Convention No. 143 of 1975 serves not only as an international legal umbrella for migrant workers, but also as a standard for recognizing, assessing, and improving work systems that can be detrimental to workers across borders. Consistent implementation of the provisions of this Convention is expected to address human rights violations against migrant workers and foster a more equitable working environment globally. Although the international human rights legal framework is quite comprehensive, its implementation still faces many challenges. One major challenge is the low rate of ratification of specific instruments for migrant workers, particularly the ICRMW, by destination countries. These countries tend to focus more on immigration control policies than on a human rights-based approach. Meanwhile, the obligation to fulfill human rights requires states to take positive action through

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policies, regulations, and administrative measures to ensure that the basic rights of irregular migrant workers are fulfilled. This obligation includes providing access to emergency health services, legal aid, and compensation mechanisms for those who become victims of exploitation. Countries of origin, transit, and destination countries have different but complementary responsibilities in protecting irregular migrant workers. Therefore, illegal migrant workers cannot be used as a reason to eliminate or reduce the protection of the human rights of illegal migrant workers. If there is a conflict between a country's laws and international responsibilities, the country must change its national laws to comply with international human rights norms, by making human rights instruments and ILO labor standards as the main reference. Because in the 1969 Vienna Convention, especially Article 27, it is emphasized that countries may not use national laws as an excuse not to implement international agreements. State sovereignty is still recognized but in the implementation of that sovereignty is limited by international obligations in human rights.

The Indonesian government has also demonstrated a strong commitment to human rights-based migration management by adopting the Global Compact for Safe, Orderly, and Regular Migration (GCM) in December 2018. This step was taken considering Indonesia's position as a country of origin, transit, and destination for migrants, including migrant workers both abroad and at home. The GCM encourages the implementation of strong, fair, humane, and gender-responsive migration policies and practices, and also strengthens cooperation between the government, civil society, and other parties to ensure safe and dignified migration. These efforts include increasing national capacity in migration management, developing evidence-based policies, and protecting migrant workers, in accordance with Indonesian migrant worker protection laws. As an example of bilateral cooperation, the Indonesian government has initiated various forms of international collaboration with migrant worker destination countries, such as Malaysia, to reduce the practice of illegally sending migrant workers while increasing their protection. One preventative measure taken is through maritime security diplomacy and cooperation. Cooperation in patrols between Indonesia and Malaysia to combat illegal migration and human trafficking is an application of bilateral maritime defense and security diplomacy.

This is carried out through various forums such as the Malindo General Border Committee (GBC) and coordinated patrols (Patkor Malindo). Although to date not fully supported by a legally binding bilateral legal framework, this aims to deter the flow of illegal migration through waterways. Joint patrols in border areas, especially in vulnerable locations such as the waters of the Riau Islands and unofficial ports, are aimed at preventing the illegal sending of migrant workers, which is often carried out by human trafficking networks. However, the effectiveness of this measure depends heavily on how well the coordination between agencies and the commitment to law enforcement of both countries. In a broader context, regional cooperation within the ASEAN framework should be utilized optimally as a tool to strengthen solidarity and collective responses between countries in dealing with cross-border migration issues. Therefore, bilateral and multilateral approaches need to be strengthened so that handling illegal migration focuses not only on physical border controls but also includes improving legal aspects, protecting victims of human trafficking, and enhancing the capacity of relevant migration agencies. Despite various efforts, the reality is that illegal migration routes remain active, and human trafficking networks are increasingly adept at evading surveillance. This situation underscores the importance of a complementary, community-based approach, particularly through increasing legal knowledge and public awareness regarding the risks of illegal migration, legal migration procedures, and existing legal protection mechanisms.

CONCLUSION

After conducting the analysis, it can be concluded that undocumented migrant workers are still considered legal subjects in the context of international human rights and have fundamental rights that cannot be denied solely because of their immigration status. The principles of universality and the prohibition of discrimination in international human rights law affirm that every individual, regardless of nationality or migration status, has the right to respect, protection, and access to justice. International instruments such as the Universal Declaration of Human Rights (UDHR), the International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights (ICCPR), and the International Covenant on Economic, Social, and Cultural Rights (ICESCR) provide the normative basis that these rights apply to "every person" within a country's territory. The International Labour Organization (ILO), through Convention No. 143 of 1975, provides significant protection for undocumented migrant workers in the employment context. The ILO emphasizes that violations of immigration status are administrative offenses and should not deprive workers of basic rights, such as the right to wages, good working conditions, and protection from exploitation. In this way, the ILO's approach reinforces the view that protecting illegal migrant workers is not only an immigration issue, but also a human rights and social justice issue.

SUGGESTION

Based on these conclusions, the author makes several recommendations as follows:

1. For destination countries, it is recommended that they integrate a human rights-based approach into their immigration and employment policies, ensuring that immigration law enforcement does not disregard the fundamental rights of undocumented migrant workers. Countries should also strengthen labor oversight and provide undocumented migrant workers with secure access to complaints and legal aid.
2. For countries of origin, it is necessary to increase preventive protection efforts through education on safe migration, strengthening consular protection, and bilateral and multilateral cooperation with destination countries to ensure the protection of the rights of their citizens working abroad, including those in irregular situations.
3. The UN and the International Labour Organization (ILO) are committed to continuing to encourage the ratification and effective implementation of international instruments such as the ICRMW and ILO Convention No. 143 of 1975. Furthermore, monitoring systems for practices that may violate the rights of undocumented migrant workers need to be strengthened. National policymakers are also urged to align national laws with international human rights standards, ensuring that migration and labor policies are non-discriminatory and provide equal and humane protection to all migrant workers.

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